

MESON MASS RELATIONS IN BROKEN SU(4) WITH NEARLY IDEAL MIXING.

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In the following we shall investigate some of the consequences of the following assumptions:

- (i) The strong interactions are approximately SU(4) -symmetric. In particular, the recently discovered particle $\psi(3100)^{1)}$ is an $I_{GJ}^{PC} = 0^{-}1^{--}$ vector meson belonging to the $\underline{1} + \underline{15}$ representation of SU(4) together with the conventional vector mesons ρ , ω , ϕ , K^* and the yet undiscovered charmed vector mesons D^* and F^* .
- (ii) The naive quark model describing mesons as $\bar{q}q$ bound states applies ($q = u, d, s, c$). The ψ is a ${}^3S_1 \bar{c}c$ state. The quarks behave, within the range of hadronic forces, exactly as pointlike particles with spin 1/2.
- (iii) The equality of the masses is destroyed by a SU(4) -breaking interaction containing two terms transforming like the states $|\underline{15}, \underline{1}, 000\rangle$ and $|\underline{15}, \underline{8}, 000\rangle$ (in the

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notation $|SU(4), SU(3), II_3 Y\rangle$. In the quark model language the symmetry is broken by having quark mass differences, $m_u = m_d$, $m_s - m_u = \Delta_s > 0$, $m_c - m_u = \Delta_c > \Delta_s$.

- (iv) This breaking interaction also mixes the $I = I_3 = Y = 0$ particles in such a way that the physical states are nearly ideal,

$$\begin{aligned} |\omega\rangle &\approx \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (|\bar{u}u\rangle + |\bar{d}d\rangle) \equiv |\Omega\rangle \\ |\phi\rangle &\approx |\bar{s}s\rangle \equiv |S\rangle \\ |\psi\rangle &\approx |\bar{c}c\rangle \equiv |C\rangle \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

- (v) Another source of symmetry breaking is allowed for by having different space wave functions for the 15-states and the singlet state, so that the overlap integral becomes

$$J_{15,1} = \int d\tau \psi_{15}^* \psi_1 \neq 1. \quad (2)$$

In fact the symmetry breaking is then equivalent to the Ansatz of refs. 2, 3, 4 for chiral $U(4) \otimes U(4)$ breaking.

Consider the frame formed by the three $I = Y = C = 0$ states

$$\begin{aligned} |15, 8\rangle &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{6}} (|\bar{u}u\rangle + |\bar{d}d\rangle - 2|\bar{s}s\rangle) \\ |15, 1\rangle &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{12}} (|\bar{u}u\rangle + |\bar{d}d\rangle + |\bar{s}s\rangle - 3|\bar{c}c\rangle) \\ |1, 1\rangle &= \frac{1}{2} (|\bar{u}u\rangle + |\bar{d}d\rangle + |\bar{s}s\rangle + |\bar{c}c\rangle). \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

The states (3) mix to form the physical states $|\omega\rangle$, $|\phi\rangle$ and $|\psi\rangle$. These are the eigenstates of the operator

$$M = \sum_{q=u,d,s,c} m_q + V, \quad (4)$$

where V is a $SU(4)$ -symmetric potential term. M and m_q stand for either linear or quadratic masses^{*}). Using the quark mass differences Δ_s and Δ_c and the overlap integral (2), the matrix of the operator (4) can be written in the basis (3) as

$$M = \begin{pmatrix} m_{15,8} & -\frac{\sqrt{2}}{3} \Delta_s & -\sqrt{\frac{2}{3}} \Delta_s J_{15,1} \\ & m_{15,1} & -\frac{\sqrt{3}}{2} (\Delta_c - \frac{1}{3} \Delta_s) J_{15,1} \\ \text{complex} & & \\ \text{conjugate terms} & & m_{11} \end{pmatrix}. \quad (5)$$

The physical states $|\omega\rangle$, $|\phi\rangle$, $|\psi\rangle$ are the eigenvectors of (5) and the eigenvalues are ω , ϕ , ψ (we use the particle symbol to denote the mass or mass squared). Some of the parameters in (5) can be expressed in terms of the known ρ and K^* masses:

$$\Delta_s = K^* - \rho$$

$$m_{15,8} = \frac{4}{3} K^* - \frac{1}{3} \rho$$

$$m_{15,1} = m_{15,8} + \frac{3}{2} \Delta_c - \frac{7}{6} \Delta_s$$

Thus the diagonalization procedure provides us with 3 equations

^{*}) We make no a priori assumption about the power with which the masses should enter.

to determine 3 unknowns: m_{11} , Δ_c and $J_{15,1}$.

Let us now use assumption (iv). It is well known that the vector mesons are nearly ideally mixed in $SU(3)$. Moreover, the $\psi(3100)$ must be a nearly pure $|\bar{c}c\rangle$ state. Thus it may be advantageous to transform the mass matrix (5) to the ideal frame (1) where it can be expected to be nearly diagonal. The transformation is done by

$$M_{\text{ideal}} = \tilde{C} M C$$

where

$$C = \begin{pmatrix} \sqrt{1/3} & -\sqrt{2/3} & 0 \\ \sqrt{1/6} & \sqrt{1/12} & -\sqrt{3/4} \\ \sqrt{1/2} & \sqrt{1/4} & \sqrt{1/4} \end{pmatrix}$$

Replacing m_{11} and $J_{15,1}$ by

$$m_{11} = 4\mu_0 + \frac{1}{2} (K^* + \rho + \Delta_c)$$

$$J_{15,1} = 1 + 2\gamma$$

where the unknowns are μ_0 and γ (μ_0 separates the representations 1 and 15 and γ determines their mixing), the diagonal elements of M_{ideal} become:

$$m_{\Omega} = (2\mu_0 - \gamma\Delta_c) + \rho - \gamma\Delta_s$$

$$m_S = \frac{1}{2}(2\mu_0 - \gamma\Delta_c) + 2K^* - \rho + \frac{3}{2}\gamma\Delta_s \quad (6)$$

$$m_C = \frac{1}{2}(2\mu_0 - \gamma\Delta_c) + 2\Delta_c(1+\gamma) - \frac{1}{2}\Delta_s(1+\gamma) + \frac{1}{2}(K^* + \rho).$$

We can see that it is accidentally possible to eliminate two of the three unknowns simultaneously, because of the presence of the combination $(2\mu_0 - \gamma\Delta_c)$ in all the three equations. The Eqs. (6) then simplify to

$$1 + \gamma = \frac{2m_S - m_\Omega - \rho}{4(K^* - \rho)} \quad (7)$$

$$1 + \gamma = \frac{m_C - m_S}{2(D^* - K^*)} \quad (8)$$

$$1 + \gamma = \frac{2m_C - m_\Omega - \rho}{4(D^* - \rho)} \quad (9)$$

Consider now the full matrix M_{ideal} . The off-diagonal elements are small, of order $\epsilon\Delta_S$ with $\epsilon \lesssim 0.3$. On the diagonal we will have

$$\omega = m_\Omega + O(\epsilon^2\Delta_S)$$

$$\phi = m_S + O(\epsilon^2\Delta_S)$$

$$\psi = m_C + O(\epsilon^2\Delta_S)$$

Thus to order $\epsilon^2\Delta_S$ we can replace the masses m_Ω , m_S , m_C of the ideal states by the physical masses ω , ϕ and ψ . Eq. (7) then becomes

$$1 + \gamma = \frac{2\phi - \omega - \rho}{4K^* - \rho}, \quad (10)$$

permitting the determination of γ (to order $\epsilon\Delta_S/\Delta_c$) from

conventional vector mesons only.

Taking the ρ^0 mass to be 0.77 ± 0.01 GeV, the K^{*0} mass to be 0.8965 GeV and the ω and ϕ masses as tabulated in Review of Particle Properties⁵⁾, we find

$$\gamma = -0.04 \begin{matrix} -0.05 \\ +0.06 \end{matrix} \quad \text{for linear masses}$$

$$\gamma = +0.04 \begin{matrix} -0.05 \\ +0.06 \end{matrix} \quad \text{for quadratic masses.}$$

Thus γ is consistent with zero.

To order $\epsilon^2 \Delta_S$ and $\epsilon \Delta_S / \Delta_C$ Eq. (10) furnishes a new mass relation for nearly ideally mixed mesons,

$$3\rho = 4K^{*} - 2\phi + \omega. \quad (11)$$

Note that this relation does not contain particles requiring a higher symmetry than SU(3). It can be derived in any SU(n), $n > 3$, in an analogous way, and it will hold to order $\epsilon^2 \Delta_S$ and $\epsilon \Delta_S / \Delta_i$, where $\Delta_i = m_i - m_u$ ($i=c, \dots$ quarks). In SU(3), the relation (11) will hold only to order $\epsilon \Delta_S$. However, if the quark dynamics is such that the overlap integrals should be inserted into the off-diagonal elements of M only after the rotation to the ideal frame (1), the relation (11) will be true to order $\epsilon^2 \Delta_S$ in all SU(n).

To the same order, the Eqs. (8) and (9) furnish the mass relations

$$2(D^{*} - K^{*}) = \psi - \phi \quad (12)$$

$$4(D^{*-}\rho) = 2\psi - \omega - \rho. \quad (13)$$

Since the $J^P = 2^+$ mesons are also nearly ideally mixed in SU(3), the relations (11) - (13) are also expected to hold for them. Only Eq. (11) can be checked with the conventional 2^+ mesons. It is true to (2+9) % for linear masses and to (5+6) % for quadratic masses.

If one makes the cruder approximation of setting

$$\omega = \rho \quad (14)$$

in Eq. (11) one obtains the Gell-Mann-Okubo mass formula. Eq. (14) is, however, true only to order $\epsilon\Delta_S$.

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